

WAYS TO INCREASE LITERACY IN A MOTHER TONGUE LESSON

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Annotation. "Mother tongue" is a science that not only teaches lexical and grammatical norms, but also serves to develop the potential for the student to use Optional Subject, subject-cross-section texts, correct reading, orthoepic and orthographic norms in his oratory activities. In this article, we want to Share our thoughts with educators about today's circulation, that is, about the methods that can be used for students to achieve spelling literacy.

Keywords: grammatical norms, grammatical rules, spelling rule, correct writing, correct displacement, reflection.

The main four types of speech activity, which is acquired by teaching the language to the student in this language: the development of the norm of skills and skills, which is assumed in each class in the practice of listening and understanding speech, speaking, reading and writing, being able to independently exchange ideas and express thoughts in various speech situations that occur in the process of the dynamics of obtaining information by reading sources, mastering the skills of entering into communication in the way of expressing their attitude to events are envisaged. For the logical, critical, creative thinking of the student, special attention is paid to understanding by reading in the lessons of the native language. A student who has mastered his native language will satisfactorily master other subjects. A student with excellent reading literacy will think logically, critically, creatively by reading the texts he is studying in other subjects, the ability to apply the knowledge gained in life is developed. It is also one of the main tasks before the teacher to adapt practical assignments designed to work with texts that comply with the requirements

of the International Assessment Program (PISA, PIRLS), aimed at forming the logical thinking and practical skills of the student. It provides for the formation of skills for understanding the text, analytical, critical thinking and reacting. Mother tongue is a national literacy discipline.

Because by teaching this subject perfectly, it is possible to achieve literacy of students. During the teaching of the subject of mother tongue, we also pay special attention to the spelling literacy, which is the most important aspect, in addition to providing students with information about the history of our language, the variety of words, their making, linguistic departments, sources of enrichment of words. The rules in textbooks also encourage spelling literacy. This helps the student to put into practice the theoretical knowledge acquired. Nevertheless, a number of spelling errors sometimes occur in the texts of the reader's written control work: dictation, statement, essay, composition. It is especially a pity that students hesitate, think and even replace these letters when writing words in which the letters x and h are present. This situation leads us educators to work even more on the written literacy of students, to explain the correct spelling of such words to students in easy ways. I would like to share my recommendations in this regard. There are a lot of words in our language in which the letters x and h are involved. It is imperative to memorize in a separate vocabulary how these words are written full of readers. When these words are used more in their place on the necessary topics and the spelling is explained, the readers will easily master it. It was useful in the newly published textbooks that it was exercises, texts that were given to work with dictionaries. Even then, literacy is not worthy of praise, as a result of the fact that students' desire to teach is excellent, that a culture of reading has not been formed, that they have been prepared for classes since beyond. We also have talented, ingenious students with a high level of correct literacy. We specifically touched on this issue for the reason that our problem was to ensure the literacy of our young people.

Written control work(dictation, statement, essay) written in the next lesson after receipt work analysis is carried out. A self-assessment method can be used in

this. The teacher in this lesson says the words with the letters x and h, which, after working on errors in the control work of students, are actively used in the colloquial style, inactive in the artistic style. After the students are written, the screen displays the spelling of these words. Readers examine the words written in their notebooks on the screen themselves and put their grades on themselves. For example: harkhasha, most likely, hihilaq, haytavur, hijjalaq, hayhatday, hayfsan, hayhaylam, sensitive, airy, khakhalam, trifle, spend, fluff... like. We need to bring as many such words into the written speech of students as possible so that they can write with the letter X and h in error. As the great educator said, "repetition is the mother of knowledge." The use of the "reflection" method is also one of the most effective.

In this case, a dictionary dictation, or text, compiled from exactly the same difficult words that are constantly repeated, can be selected. The work is reused in several classes and the student is remembered. With this method, words are selected that differ in the letters d-t, g-k, z-s, v-f, x-h, n-m, in which students make many mistakes. The game - Method "move and remember" is also one of the effective methods. In doing so, the teacher gives the students an artistic text to move and is tasked with remembering the words given in that text. For example, it can also be said that we get a dictation from this text. The text is carefully copied by the reader and tries to write without errors. Also get a dictation from this text. Almost 50% of students, but more than undanam, write in error-free grades "4" and "5". Do you say this is wrong? Why is it not your achievement that he now corresponded without errors? We teachers try to find more mistakes of our students. We forget that these mistakes are actually ours. Readers are only our face, a means of bringing our labor to the surface. Let's focus on finding mistakes and fixing those mistakes! Then our result will definitely be. It takes a little extra work from us. Because it is a daily task beyond controls. Through this task, the reader also gains a culture of reading. He will not only pay attention to the meaning of all the words he reads, but will also learn to write carefully. Bored with this, he asks "who is literate?!" game is also useful. Condition: the Class is divided into subgroups. Each group verbally tells the

opposing team a word that the spelling should write without errors, and team representatives write on the board. Very interesting and useful game method. Through this method, students learn, teach, and learn to be attentive. From my experience, I will clearly say that your group will be literate and ingenious if you allocate literacy minutes once a week for 1-2 years from your lesson and apply similar techniques. Increasing literacy, reading words carefully, you also move to all subject textbooks and educate students who can read well in other subjects. When a student cannot apply the theoretical knowledge he has acquired in practice, we cannot say that he gave birth to it.

There was also a greater emphasis on literacy when the recruitment process after graduation of higher education institutions was tested with a conversational and literacy rate (such as dictation or writing one of the work papers). If a person is in demand, he will diligently try to fulfill this requirement. With this method, it is possible to increase the written literacy of students, as well as future personnel. Every citizen who can speak and write correctly in the language of the state will be living with a sense of civil duty, a sense of belonging to the country.

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